

Where to cut-off ? Endocrine hazard profiles of EBI fungicides

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Endocrine cut-off criterion

- Regarding wildlife, the new EU pesticide regulation 1107/2009 EEC requires: "An active substance... shall only be approved if... it is not considered to have endocrine disrupting properties that may cause adverse effects on non-target organisms..."
- Thereby, a paradigm shift in regulatory decision making was introduced for this specific mode of toxic action: hazard-based instead of risk-based.
- Specific scientific criteria for regulatory classification of pesticides with endocrine disrupting properties are not provided in the new regulation (to be proposed by EU commission by end of 2013).

Ergosterol Biosynthesis Inhibitors

- Fungicides of world-wide agricultural importance with widespread use in major and minor crops.
- Active substances of this heterogeneous chemical group (triazoles, imidazoles, pyrimidines) share a similar pesticidal mode of action: inhibition of ergosterol synthesis in fungi.
- Intrinsic endocrine hazard potential of EBIs: target enzymes in fungi are partly analogous to enzymes involved in the production of sex steroid hormones in vertebrates (e.g. aromatase).
- Supposed endocrine mechanism of action of EBIs in vertebrates: Disturbance of steroidogenesis. Associated adverse effects: disturbance of sexual development (i.e. indirect anti-estrogenic if potent aromatase inhibition) and inhibition of reproduction.

Endocrine hazard profiles (wildlife)

- Case study conducted on 10 top selling EBIs in Germany (2009).
- Scientific literature and studies available from the EU review-process for active substances and from the German authorization procedure for plant protection products considered in analysis.
- Evidence for endocrine disrupting properties in-vivo and for endocrine mediated adverse effects in-vivo (only mammals and fish) is summarized in the table below.
- Proposal for differentiation in decision making: If endocrine disrupting properties are decisive for the overall hazard potential, the active substance should be considered an endocrine disruptor of regulatory concern in wildlife (i.e. cut-off applies).

Discussion

- There are noticeable differences in endocrine hazard profiles of the active substances studied which most likely reflect differences in specificity and potency (in-vitro data seem to be quite indicative in this respect).
- Chronic fish studies without endocrine specific endpoints and/or poor data quality (i.e. low statistical power to detect effects) hamper final decisions on the in-vivo relevance of the endocrine mechanism(s) suggested by in-vitro results.
- In some cases other than endocrine mediated effects may be decisive for the overall hazard potential in wildlife.
- This presentation does not anticipate official regulatory decisions to be taken in the future.

	Prochloraz	Epoxiconazole	Flusilazole	Propiconazole	Triadimenol	Difenoconazole	Tebuconazole	(Desthio-) Prothioconazole	Cyproconazole	Metconazole
Tons sold in 2009^{a)}	100 - 250	250 - 1000	25 - 100	100- 250	25 - 100	25 - 100	250 - 1000	250 - 1000	10 - 25	25 - 100
Evidence for inhibition of steroidogenesis / aromatase in-vitro^{b)}	Yes (ref. 1 - 10)	Yes (ref. 1, 4, 5, 7)	Yes (ref. 1, 7)	Yes (ref. 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11)	Yes (ref. 1, 3, 6, 7)	Yes (ref. 2, 6, 9)	Yes (ref. 1, 2, 5, 7)	No (no data)	Yes (ref. 1, 7)	No (no data)
Potency aromatase inhibition in-vitro (IC₅₀, µM)^{c)}	0.047	1.44	0.055	3.2	12.6	No data	5.8	No data	8.5	No data
Evidence for endocrine mediated (adverse) effects in-vivo: mammalian studies^{d)}	Yes: testosterone levels ↓, anogenital distance in males ↓ / in females ↑, gestation length ↑, parturition length ↑, conception rate ↓, fertility index ↓, litter loss ↑ (ref. 12, 16, 17)	Yes: disturbed steroid hormone balance, anogenital distance ↑ in females, vaginal haemorrhages, impaired fertility, gestation length ↑, dystocia (ref. 13,15)	Yes: testosterone and estradiol serum levels ↓, placental weight ↑, gestation length ↑, dystocia (ref. 12)	Yes: testosterone levels ↑, anogenital distance in males ↑, testis weight ↑ (ref. 12, 14, 15)	Yes: changes in cholesterol levels, placental weight ↑, fertility ↓, litter size ↓ (ref. 12)	No: "Information from the toxicology section gave no indications of endocrine disruption."	Yes: disturbed steroid hormone balance in males, anogenital distance ↑ in females, post-implantation loss ↑, litter size ↓ (ref. 12, 13, 15)	(Yes): ovary weight ↑, disruption of oestrus cycle, thyroid hormone levels ↓, litter size ↓, dystocia, liver toxicity observed at lower doses than repro- and developmental effects	(Yes): litter loss ↑, incidences of resorptions ↑, liver toxicity observed at lower doses than repro- and developmental effects (ref. 12)	(Yes): placental weight ↑, gestation length ↑, post implantation survival ↓, teratogenic effects observed at lower doses than repro-effects
Evidence for endocrine mediated (adverse) effects in-vivo: fish studies^{e)}	Yes: Vitellogenin in females ↓, shift in sex ratio towards males, reproduction ↓	Yes: Vitellogenin in males and females ↓, shift in sex ratio towards males, reproduction ↓	Yes: Vitellogenin in males and females ↓, sex ratio data unambiguous, reproduction ↓	(No): reproduction ↓ (study not state-of-the-art regarding endocrine specific endpoints)	(Yes): Vitellogenin in females ↓ (only screening study available, reproduction and sex ratio not assessed)	(Yes): indication for shift in sex ratio towards males and impaired reproductive performance at highest test conc.	(Yes): yolk accumulation in oocytes ↓, sexual maturation ↓, reproduction ↓, liver cell degeneration most sensitive	(Yes): indication for shift in sex ratio towards males, reproduction ↓, malformations in ELS study at clearly lower test conc.	(No): endocrine screening study negative, FLC: reproduction ↓, indication for Vitellogenin ↓ in females	(No): reproduction ↓ (Vitellogenin and sex ratio: poor data quality)
Acute-to-chronic ratio fish^{f)}	87 (reproduction, FLC)	630 (reproduction, FLC)	209 (reproduction, FLC)	140 (growth, ELS)	596 (Vitellogenin, FSA)	226 (growth males, FLC)	724 (liver toxicity, FSDT)	1985 (malformations, ELS)	118 (growth, ELS)	724 (growth, ELS)
BCF fish^{g)}	393	59.8	205	116	21	30	78	65	35	129
Other aquatic organisms clearly more sensitive than fish^{h)}	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 2.2 x lower)	No (EC ₅₀ growth <i>Lemna</i> 1.4 x lower)	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 134 x higher)	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 5.7 x higher)	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 3.3 x higher)	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 1.5 x higher)	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 1.7 x higher)	No (EC ₅₀ growth <i>green algae</i> 22 x higher)	Yes (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 7 x lower)	No (NOEC reproduction <i>Daphnia</i> 55 x higher)
Are endocrine disrupting properties decisive for the overall hazard potential in wildlife?	authors' conclusion: Yes	authors' conclusion: Yes	authors' conclusion: Yes	authors' conclusion: Inconclusive	authors' conclusion: Inconclusive	authors' conclusion: Inconclusive	authors' conclusion: Inconclusive	authors' conclusion: No	authors' conclusion: No	authors' conclusion: No
Please add your conclusion here ►	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:	your conclusion:

Table legend:

- Reported by BVL (2009) – www.bvl.bund.de
- Information from published papers only (reference numbers given in brackets).
- Concentrations at half maximum inhibition (IC₅₀) taken from Tröskén et al. (2004), i.e. the in-vitro study where a maximum number of EBIs considered here were compared study under identical experimental conditions.
- Compiled from EFSA-Conclusions and/or Draft (Re)Assessment Reports for the active substances (tox sections) and published papers (reference numbers given in brackets).
- Compiled from EFSA-Conclusions and/or Draft (Re)Assessment Reports for the active substances (ecotox sections) and/or original study reports available to UBA.
- Acute-to-chronic-ratio (ACR) = Lethal concentration (LC₅₀, mg/L) / No-observed-effect-concentration (NOEC, mg/L); the affected endpoint relevant for NOEC-derivation and study design is given in brackets. For studies without constant exposure, a calculation of time-weighted-average exposure concentrations for the suspected most sensitive life stage was conducted. Geometric mean values of LC₅₀ for a warm and a cold water species (if available) used for calculation. Low-effect-concentrations (EC₁₀ or EC₁₀₀) from some studies derived as a surrogate for NOECs have been considered. ELS: early life stage study (without endocrine-specific endpoints). FLC: full-life-cycle study (state-of-the-art FLC include endocrine specific endpoints like Vitellogenin-measurement, sex ratio determination, time-to-first-spawning, etc.). FSDT: fish-sexual-development-test (sex ratio as endocrine specific core endpoint, Vitellogenin-measurement may be included). FSA: fish screening assay (indicative assay, no endocrine specific population-relevant endpoints included, Vitellogenin-measurement as endocrine specific core endpoint).
- Bioconcentration factor (BCF, whole fish) determined in standard laboratory studies as reported in EFSA-Conclusions and/or Draft (Re)Assessment Reports for the active substances.
- Comparison with all other available acute and chronic single-species toxicity data for aquatic organisms tested in standard laboratory studies with constant exposure. Data taken from EFSA-Conclusions and/or Draft (Re)Assessment Reports for the active substances and/or UBA toxicity data base. Toxicity measure, endpoints and species for the next most sensitive aquatic organism given in brackets.

References (published papers only):

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- Kjaerstad et al. (2010): Endocrine disrupting effects in vitro of conazole antifungals used as pesticides and pharmaceuticals
- Hirnfay et al. (2006): Inhibition of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) P450 aromatase activities in brain and ovarian microsomes by various environmental substances
- Tröskén et al. (2006): Comparison of lanosterol-14-alpha-demethylase (CYP51) of human and *Candida albicans* for inhibition by different antifungal azoles
- Andersen et al. (2002): Effects of Currently Used Pesticides in Assays for Estrogenicity, Androgenicity, and Aromatase Activity in Vitro
- Sanderson & Berg (2003): Interactions of xenobiotics with the steroid hormone biosynthesis pathway
- Monod et al. (1993): Inhibition of Ovarian Microsomal Aromatase and Follicular Oestradiol Secretion by Imidazole Fungicides in Rainbow Trout
- Götz et al. (2009): Inhibition of rat and human steroidogenesis by triazole antifungals
- Zarn et al. (2003): Azole Fungicides Affect Mammalian Steroidogenesis by Inhibiting Sterol 14α-Demethylase and Aromatase
- Taxvig et al. (2007): Endocrine-Disrupting Activities In Vivo of the Fungicides Tebuconazole and Epoxiconazole
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